

POLITICAL SYSTEM OF BRITAIN, ADMINISTRATIVE DIVISION AND EDUCATION

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Abstract: The administrative-territorial division has a complex structure due to the country's constitution, which consists of a collection of documents from different historical periods. Traditionally, there are four main administrative and political divisions, traditionally called countries or regions (country).

Keywords: Britain, political system, administrative division, education, urban and rural, traditional.

All the countries that make up the UK have different statuses. In particular, Wales has never been an independent state within its current borders. After being taken over by England, it remained in a special position until 1967, when the concept of England and Wales was introduced, and is still in many respects united with England. The powers of the authorities of some countries are also determined separately in the process of devolution, which began in 1997.

From 1801, when Great Britain and Ireland were united, until 1922, when the independent state of Ireland was established, the country was officially called the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland. It is located on five thousand islands. The Channel Islands and the Isle of Man are not officially part of Great Britain, but have a special relationship with them. The Channel Islands were part of the Duchy of Normandy in the 10th century and became subject to the English crown after being handed over to France in the 15th century. The Isle of Man was under the nominal sovereignty of Norway until 1266, and in 1765 it came under the direct control of the British Crown. These territories today have their own legislatures and legal systems, and the Isle of Man also has its own tax system. The British government is solely responsible for their international representation and external defence.

Historical development led to the interstate division of Great Britain. The territory of the Great Islands is divided into very large parts: Northern Ireland, Northern Scotland, Southern Scotland, North-West, Yorkshire and the Humber region, East Midlands, West Midlands, Wales, East Anglia, South-East, South-G West and Greater London area. There is another division - divided into districts, the total number of which is 72. The speed (before indicating the city) must be indicated in the postal address with one or two letters - abbreviated. A list of these abbreviations is in any mail. Local authorities deal with housing, education, social welfare, police and fire services. They are financed by city taxes, local taxes and central government grants.

Great Britain is one of the most populous and urbanized countries in the world. On average, 1 sq. km., its area is 230 people. However, the population is very unevenly distributed across the country. The main part of the population of Great Britain is concentrated in England, which has the most favorable geographical location, favorable natural conditions and plays a leading economic role throughout the history of the British Isles. Here, the average density increases to 356 people per square meter. km. In England itself, the main industrial belt of the country, which stretches along the London-Liverpool axis, is the most densely populated: half of the population of Great Britain lives in this belt. The least populated areas are in Scotland,

its natural conditions compared to other parts of the country and less developed economy. km per 1 sq. With an average of 86 people, the population is mostly concentrated in the coasts, valleys and lowlands (especially around Glasgow and Edinburgh), with some mountainous areas almost deserted.

By the end of the 19th century. 3/4 of the population of Great Britain lived in cities, and the main type of population was already a large conurbation. Since the beginning of the twentieth century. there is an intensive migration of the rural population to the cities, where almost 4/5 of the country's population lives. In a highly urbanized country like Great Britain, it is difficult to draw a line between urban and rural settlements. Many villages have become "dormitories" for nearby cities: villagers go to work in the city every day.

One of the consequences of the development of conurbations, and especially their central cities, is excessive population density. In this regard, measures are being taken to reduce them: a part of the surplus population is moving to the suburbs or to newly expanding medium-sized cities.

There are few places in the world where seaside cities are as prominent as in the UK, with 44 of the 100 largest cities located by the sea. London first emerged as a seaport for trade with continental European nations; Trade with the countries of the Baltic Sea basin has been carried out for a long time through Gul (Hull); Bristol and Liverpool served as the "Gateway to the New World". Near major industrial centers are seaside resort towns: Brighton and Margate - near London, Blackpool - near the Lancashire coalfield, Scarborough - on the Yorkshire coast. All original buildings. attracted to the sea, all specialized apartments, and then housing. Much faster than other cities, in the past two centuries, the largest industrial centers grew near coal and iron ore mines: Glasgow, Birmingham, Manchester, Sheffield, Belfast, Middleborough, etc. The growing industry required more and more workers and laborers. Quarters were hastily built by speculators. Houses for workers are built according to a single standard. Often these are monotonous "terraces" - rows of neighboring houses of the same type. The monotony of workers' quarters in manufacturing cities is disturbed only by the smoky huge buildings of factories and plants, warehouses and gas distribution stations. The railway here, as a rule, goes to the center of the city and serves as its "skeleton". The old quarters of industrial cities are filled with new buildings, where the industrial zone is separated from the residential area.

Everywhere there are many medium-sized farms that operate without hired workers. Farms are mainly concentrated in Scotland and Wales. The densest network of villages is in north-east Yorkshire, often within 2.5 km of each other. The density of rural and semi-rural settlements is very high in the main industrial area of the country and around the Tyneside and Clydesd conurbations. Here are villages, farms and settlements where workers work in industrial enterprises interspersed with individual farms.

Most local divisions have local governments (only counties in Northern Ireland and parishes (communities) with a population of less than 150 do not). These are primarily councils directly elected by the population. Councils (local councils) term of office - four years, in Scotland - three years. Most of the councils are re-elected at the same time, each year 1/3 of the councils of the district councils of the capital districts (which includes the major cities) are re-elected. Each council annually elects from among its members (in the London boroughs and other large cities it is called the mayor, in the city it is called the lord mayor), as well as

committees that are given many of the council's powers. implementation of executive activities. Hence, there are no specific local government enforcement bodies in Great Britain. There are also no officials appointed by the central government who exercise local authority. The powers of local self-government bodies are traditional, but in practice there are difficulties in delimiting it between different levels of local self-government bodies.

It has a special status in the capital of Great Britain - London. Together with the neighboring suburbs, it forms a single conglomerate called Greater London. Traditionally, the Greater London Council was elected, which was abolished in 1985 by the Conservative government. The Labor government insisted on passing the Greater London Regeneration Act, which was announced after a referendum in the capital in May 1998. Greater London is currently governed by a 25-member Assembly and a mayor directly elected by the capital's residents. Their elections were held in May 2000.

Great Britain also owns the island and its dependencies, but they are not considered part of it. The island territories are the Isle of Man and the Channel Islands, which have belonged to England since feudal times. They are "crown" estates and subject to British sovereignty. The islands have their own governing bodies, but the English Parliament passes laws on defence, foreign relations and customs. Some regions have their own constitutions.

Great Britain is one of the largest countries of the European Union, a member of the United Nations. The capital of the country is London, its attractions are known to every schoolchild. Formerly known as the British Empire.

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